

Dynamic analysis of grid-connected hybrid wind farm

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ABSTRACT

Since the last couple of years, the expansion of grid-connected wind farms (WFs) has increased dramatically. The wind turbine might be a fixed-speed squirrel cage induction generator (FSWT-SCIG) or a variable speed wind turbine with a doubly-fed induction generator (VSWT-DFIG). The main disadvantage of FSWT-SCIG is its lack of ability to adjust power quality. Inversely, the VSWT-DFIG is a competitive wind turbine technology that allows for the effective management of both active and reactive power outputs. Moreover, it has some extraordinary functionalities rather than FSWT-SCIG. However, the major downside to this system is that it only has a partial rating AC/DC/AC power converter, which is extremely expensive. Hence, to reduce the overall cost combining the implementation of VSWT-DFIG and FSWT-SCIG in a WF could be a feasible alternative. Therefore, a novel DFIG control technique is proposed in this article, which can keep the connection point voltage of the hybrid WF stable during dynamic analysis. To evaluate the proposed controller responses PSCAD/EMTDC software has been used.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The huge usage of fossil fuels, market volatility, and growing concern for the environment have all indicated the need for renewable and clean energy sources in recent history. Furthermore, renewable energy sources are practically unlimited, free, clean, and easily accessible. The wind market had a phenomenal year in 2019, as it installed 60.4 GW of systems, making it the second largest in history. Furthermore, the global cumulative wind power (WP) capacity reaches up to 651 GW which is highlighting 19% growth of year-over-year (YoY). Meanwhile, onshore wind new installations reached 54.2 GW, even while offshore wind recent units exceeded 6 GW, accounting for 10% of overall new installations in 2019, the fastest-growing percentage to date. Moreover, based on the Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC), nearly 355 GW of new installation will be incorporated in the following five years, with a yearly installment rate of 71 GW until 2024. Therefore, WP might satisfy up to 20% of worldwide power demand by 2030, exceeding 2010 GW. However, worldwide the WP sector gets affected because of the novel COVID-19 virus. Through these difficulties, the GWEC has determined to preserve its critical factors unaffected, and when the world will recover from this pandemic, it would take proactive measures to manage the situation [1], [2]. Stability is

significantly affected by the enormous quantity of WP incorporated into the power system. All the wind farms (WFs) must need to stay in stable condition during the long run.

Fixed-speed wind turbines with squirrel cage induction generators (FSWT-SCIGs) are by far the most often employed wind turbines (WTs) since they are easy to build, robust, and most importantly they are cost-effective [3]. Despite this, the SCIG is directly tied to the electrical grid and as the voltage of a bus-connected FSWT-SCIG based WF fluctuates significantly during starting phase, a sufficient amount of reactive power is required [4], [5]. Nevertheless, at the steady state phase, SCIG requires reactive power. Hence, a capacitor bank is utilized to supply reactive power [6]. Therefore, to make the terminal voltage stable several flexible AC transmissions (FACTS) device has been used, such as static synchronous compensator (STATCOM) [7]–[11], energy capacitor system (ECS) [12], static var compensator (SVC) [13], thyristor-controlled series capacitor (TCSC) [14], static synchronous series compensator (SSSC) [15], and superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES) [16]. Therefore, the overall expenditures have been increased.

Nevertheless, variable speed wind turbine with a doubly-fed induction generator (VSWT-DFIG) is one of the most competitive wind turbines in the wind industry. Since it has some remarkable benefits VSWT-DFIG has a massive market share in the world, such as high efficiency, lower converter rating, reliable control on active and reactive power, and lightweight [17], [18]. The control of the rotor side converter (RSC), which is commonly rated at around 30% of the generator rating when the rotor speed is between 75% and 125% under standard conditions, is predominantly responsible for these benefits [19]. Apart from this, the key disadvantage of VSWT-DFIG-based WFs is they are quite expensive due to their partial rating power electronic AC/DC/AC converter. Hence, hybrid installation of FSWT-SCIG and VSWT-DFIG has been implemented. As a result, SCIG's stability may be achieved at a cheaper cost. Consequently, the foremost objective of this study is the develop a novel DFIG control strategy that focuses on the PI controller to regulate the RSC controller's outer and inner loop in order to keep the connection point voltage of the hybrid WF stable during dynamic analysis. The following section is presented as follows, section 2 is the model of power system, section 3 is the DFIG system with the cascaded control system, section 4 is the proposed controller, section 5 is the grid-side converter (GSC) controller, section 6 is simulation analysis and discussion, and section 7 is conclusion.

2. MODEL OF POWER SYSTEM

A double circuit transmission line and transformers with voltage ratings of 0.69 kV/6.6 kV and 6.6 kV/66 kV are employed to connect the SCIG and DFIG to an infinite bus in the power system architecture illustrated in Figure 1. The required and the power rating of both WTs are 35 MW and 15 MW, respectively. The base power of the system has been chosen 100 MVA and the frequency has been chosen 50 Hz. All the essential attributes of both generators have been taken from [20].

Figure 1. Power system model

3. DFIG SYSTEM WITH CASCADED CONTROLLER

Figure 2 shows the MPPT curve of DFIG system [21]. According to the available wind speed, the MPPT curve for DFIG is segmented into four functioning regions as described in the following [22]: i) minimum operating region from point A to point B, ii) optimal speed region from point B to point C, iii) maximum operating region from point C to point D, and iv) the limited speed region where the pitch controller take action. Besides, Figure 3 shows the layout of VSWT-DFIG and its controller. Aerodynamic wind turbine system with drive-train, wound rotor induction generator (WRIG), pitch angle controller, RSC, and GSC comprise up the system. Two levels of insulated gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs) are employed to regulate the RSC and GSC. However, WRIG transforms WP into electrical power. The rotor position (θ_r) and speed (ω_r) are collected from the WRIG rotor shaft. As demonstrated in Figure 3, the stator junction is directly coupled to the grid while the rotor is coupled to the grid via RSC and GSC. The power converter rating is one-third of the WRIG rating. The RSC supplies the rotor windings variable frequency excitement according to the

wind speed and integrates the GSC through the transformer with the grid system. This work employs the pulse width modulation (PWM) approach, with a carrier frequency of 3.0 kHz for both converters. In the DC-Link circuit is a DC chopper. The comparator block is in charge of it. The comparator triggers the DC chopper and protects the DC-Link circuit when the DC-link voltage (V_{dc}) is 1.15 pu. The rated voltage is 1.2 kV.

Figure 2. MPPT diagram of DFIG

Figure 3. DFIG system with cascaded controller

In the synchronous reference frame, the DFIG system is defined. Using (1) and (2), the d and q-axis stator and rotor voltages are calculated [23].

$$\begin{cases} V_{sd} = R_s \cdot i_{sd} + \frac{d\varphi_{sd}}{dt} - \omega_s \cdot \varphi_{sq} \\ V_{sq} = R_s \cdot i_{sq} + \frac{d\varphi_{sq}}{dt} + \omega_s \cdot \varphi_{sd} \\ V_{rd} = R_r \cdot i_{rd} + \frac{d\varphi_{rd}}{dt} - \omega_r \cdot \varphi_{rq} \\ V_{rq} = R_r \cdot i_{rq} + \frac{d\varphi_{rq}}{dt} + \omega_r \cdot \varphi_{rd} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{cases} \varphi_{sd} = L_{st} i_{sd} + L_m i_{rd} \\ \varphi_{sq} = L_{st} i_{sq} + L_m i_{rq} \\ \varphi_{rd} = L_{rt} i_{rd} + L_m i_{sd} \\ \varphi_{rq} = L_{rt} i_{rq} + L_m i_{sq} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In the (1) and (2), R_s , R_r and L_{st} , L_{rt} are represented the resistance and self-inductance of stator and rotor winding accordingly. Mutual inductance is illustrated as L_m . Also, i_{sd} , i_{sq} , i_{rd} , and i_{rq} are represented the currents of stator and rotor sequentially. Consequently, ω_r represents the angular speed of the rotor and the angular frequency of the grid is presented as ω_s .

4. PROPOSED RSC CONTROLLER

As displayed in Figure 3, the RSC is regulated by the RSC controller. Four PI controllers are used in the control system to adjust several errors. The outer loop is responsible of acquiring MPPT power from the DFIG as well as reactive power regulation. The inner loop is employed to control the d and q -axis currents. To adjust active power, losses in the turbine, rotor, and stator are taken into consideration which is displayed in the following equation to maximize reactive power supply.

$$P_s = (i_{sd}^2 + i_{sq}^2)R_s \quad (3)$$

$$P_r = (i_{rd}^2 + i_{rq}^2)R_r \quad (4)$$

$$P_{tl} = 0.01\omega_r \quad (5)$$

The stator, rotor, and turbine losses are denoted by P_s , P_r and P_{tl} , accordingly. The active power extracted can be more realistically estimated by accounting for all these losses. The voltage dip at the common coupling point is employed to regulate the reactive power. The reference reactive power was calculated as regards [24], [25].

$$Q_{ref} = S \left\{ \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{V}{V_0} \right)^{12} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Where, the rated apparent power is represented by S , the terminal voltage and pre-fault voltage (1.0 pu) of DFIG are represented by V and V_0 . Besides, depending upon (6), the voltage vs reactive power features curve is displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Voltage vs reactive power features curve

5. GSC CONTROLLER

Figure 3 additionally depicts the GSC controller, which has four PI controllers to adjust for several other error signals. Furthermore, the GSC reactive power (Q) and DC-link voltage (V_{dc}) are regulated sequentially by the d-axis (I_{gd}) and q-axis (I_{gq}) current components. In addition, the reference reactive power is zero, and the reference DC-link voltage is 1.2 kV (1.0 pu).

6. SIMULATION ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The dynamic behavior of the proposed RSC controller of DFIG is illustrated and evaluated in this section. The power system represented in Figure 1 is employed to evaluate the performance. The overall simulation is executed for 100.0 s.

However, the actual wind speed for both WFs as shown in Figure 5 is recorded intending to monitor the dynamic effects of the proposed power system. Figures 6 and 7 represent the active power and reactive power response at the common coupling point (PCC). Figure 8 shows the voltage response at the PCC, and it is clearly evident that the terminal voltage is remains constant.

Figure 5. Wind speed for SCIG and DFIG

Figure 6. Active power at common coupling point (PCC)

Figure 7. Reactive power at common coupling point (PCC)

Figure 8. Voltage at common coupling point (PCC)

Hence, the system remains in stable condition. Moreover, the active power output for both WFs is displayed in Figures 9 and 10. Besides, Figures 11 and 12 depict the reactive power output for both WFs (SCIG & DFIG). Finally, Figure 13 displays the DC-link voltage of DFIG, which stays nearly steady during the whole simulation run time.

Figure 9. Active power output of SCIG

Figure 10. Active power output of DFIG

Figure 11. Reactive power output of SCIG

Figure 12. Reactive power output of DFIG

Figure 13. DC-link voltage output of DFIG

7. CONCLUSION

This study proposes a novel DFIG control system to increase the system stability of SCIG based WFs with partial integration of the DFIG WF. The total installation cost of WFs might be decreased with this hybrid WF concept. Furthermore, the simulation analysis reveals that the suggested RSC controller is capable of confirming constant terminal voltage during dynamic analysis. Hence, the proposed control scheme is ensuring system stability.

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